

Optimizing Embedding-Based Video Recommendation in Spanish Using LLMs for Automated Model and Parameter Selection

Ignacio Despujol Zabala¹[0000-0003-2776-1638], Carlos Turró Ribalta²[0000-0002-3840-9405],
Jaime Busquets Mataix, Sergio Puche García

^{1,2,3,4} Universitat Politècnica de València, Camino de Vera sn 46021 Valencia, Spain
ndespujol@asic.upv.es¹, turro@cc.upv.es², busquets@asic.upv.es³,
spuche@upv.es⁴

Abstract. This study investigates the automation of an embedding-based video recommendation system in Spanish through the application of Large Language Models (LLMs). The primary objective was to determine the optimal embedding model, search strategy, and chunking parameters for a system designed to deliver the top 5 most relevant videos in response to user queries. To achieve this, we developed an automated testing framework.

A dataset of 400 randomly selected videos from a pool of 50,000 was used. GPT-4 was employed to generate 10 questions per video, which were subsequently refined to remove irrelevant queries. These questions served as the basis for evaluating and comparing the performance of various models and configurations. The evaluation metric measured the percentage of instances in which the system accurately retrieved the source video within the top 1 and top 5 recommendations. This evaluation was conducted across different embedding models, search strategies, and chunking parameters.

Keywords: embeddings, recommendation system, LLM, AI model.

1 Introduction

Video recommendation systems have become an integral part of modern digital platforms, enhancing user experience and driving engagement. Traditional recommendation systems often rely on collaborative filtering or content-based approaches, but these methods can be limited in their ability to capture the semantic and contextual nuances of video content, especially in question-based retrieval scenarios where users explicitly state their information needs.

1.1 Traditional Question-to-Video Recommendation Approaches

Early question-based video recommendation systems relied on simple keyword matching between user queries and video metadata. Collaborative filtering approaches, introduced by Goldberg et al. (1992), were adapted to this context by analyzing how similar users' queries led to similar video selections. Such systems recommended videos that

were frequently watched by users who asked similar questions, regardless of the actual content's relevance to the query.

Content-based filtering, as detailed by Pazzani and Billsus (2007), found a natural application in query-based systems by matching question terms against video metadata like titles, descriptions, and tags. For instance, a query about "how to change a car tire" would trigger recommendations for videos containing these keywords in their metadata.

A fundamental approach underpinning many early question-to-video systems was the Bag-of-Words (BoW) model, described by Lewis (1998) as a simple yet effective text representation technique. In BoW, both user questions and video metadata were treated as unordered collections of words, disregarding grammar and word order. This representation allowed for straightforward similarity calculations based on term overlap. For example, a question like "How do I bake chocolate chip cookies?" would be transformed into a multiset of terms: {"how", "do", "i", "bake", "chocolate", "chip", "cookies"}, which could then be matched against similarly processed video descriptions. While computationally efficient, this approach suffered from an inability to capture word order relationships (failing to distinguish "how to train your dog" from "how your dog trains you") and semantic relationships between terms (not recognizing that "baking" and "cooking" are related concepts).

These early approaches faced significant challenges: poor handling of synonyms and paraphrases (users asking the same question in different ways), inability to understand the intent behind questions, and limited semantic matching between natural language queries and video content. Additionally, they struggled with the vocabulary mismatch problem identified by Furnas et al. (1987), when users and content creators used different terminology for the same concepts.

1.2 The Evolution Through Sparse Vector Representations

Information retrieval techniques became increasingly important as question-based video recommendation systems evolved. The Vector Space Model (Salton et al., 1975) represented both queries and video metadata as sparse vectors in a high-dimensional term space, enabling similarity calculations to rank videos by relevance to the query.

Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF), introduced by Salton and McGill (1983), improved keyword matching by weighting terms based on their specificity. In question-based video retrieval, this meant that unique terms in a user's question (e.g., "carburetor" in an auto repair question) would carry more weight than common terms (e.g., "how" or "to").

Extending the basic Bag-of-Words approach, N-gram models (Cavnar & Trenkle, 1994) incorporated some word order information by considering sequences of N adjacent words. This allowed systems to distinguish between phrases like "White House" (as a single concept) and the separate words "white" and "house." When applied to

question-based video retrieval, N-gram models enabled more precise matching between query phrases and video content, particularly for questions containing distinct multi-word concepts or technical terminology. For example, a bi-gram representation of "how to make sourdough bread" would capture phrases like "sourdough bread" as distinct units, improving matches to relevant baking videos.

Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA/LSI) by Deerwester et al. (1990) helped address the synonymy problem by projecting queries and video descriptions into a lower-dimensional semantic space. This allowed systems to recognize that a question about "automobile maintenance" might match videos tagged with "car repair" even without exact keyword matches.

Query expansion techniques, surveyed by Carpineto and Romano (2012), were employed to augment user questions with related terms, addressing vocabulary mismatch issues. For instance, a query about "DSLR photography tips" might be expanded to include "camera," "lens," or "aperture" to better match relevant instructional videos.

While these sparse vector approaches improved question-to-video matching, they still struggled with understanding the semantic intent behind queries and the rich multimodal content of videos. Their inability to capture deeper question meaning and contextual nuances limited recommendation quality, especially for complex or ambiguous queries.

1.3 The Embedding Revolution in Question-Based Video Recommendation

The introduction of dense word embeddings revolutionized question-based video recommendation systems. Word2Vec, introduced by Mikolov et al. (2013a, 2013b), enabled systems to represent both user questions and video transcriptions in a continuous vector space that preserved semantic relationships in the vector values. This allowed for more nuanced matching between queries and videos, even with few exact keywords in common.

GloVe (Global Vectors), developed by Pennington et al. (2014), further improved semantic representations by analyzing global co-occurrence statistics. These embedding approaches enabled question-based systems to understand that a query about "beginner yoga poses" semantically relates to videos about "simple stretches for yoga newcomers" without relying on exact term matches.

The embedding revolution progressed further with sentence and document-level representations. Skip-Thought Vectors (Kiros et al., 2015) and later models like Universal Sentence Encoder (Cer et al., 2018) enabled encoding entire questions as dense vectors, capturing question meaning holistically rather than as a bag of words.

Transformative advancements came with the introduction of BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) by Devlin et al. (2019) and similar

contextual embedding models. These approaches recognize that questions have context-dependent meanings and can capture nuances like:

Question intent classification: Distinguishing between informational questions ("How do solar panels work?"), instructional queries ("How to install solar panels"), and opinion-seeking questions ("Are solar panels worth the investment?").

Entity and relationship understanding: Recognizing entities in questions and their relationships, enabling better matching to relevant videos.

Context-dependent term understanding: Capturing that "python" in a question about programming differs from "python" in a wildlife query.

Modern question-based video recommendation systems leverage these embedding technologies alongside specialized components:

Question understanding modules that parse user queries to extract intent, entities, and implicit information needs.

Cross-modal embeddings that represent both textual queries and video content (including visual features, audio, and transcripts) in a shared vector space, enabling direct relevance matching as described by Wang et al. (2018).

Transformer-based architectures like CLIP (Radford et al., 2021) that align natural language and visual content, allowing systems to match questions directly to visual concepts in videos.

Attention mechanisms that focus on the most relevant aspects of videos given a specific question, as demonstrated by Lei et al. (2020) in their moment-based retrieval system.

The most advanced question-based video recommendation systems now employ dense retrievers and re-rankers. First, efficient approximate nearest neighbor search finds candidate videos with embeddings similar to the question embedding. Then, more compute-intensive transformer models re-rank these candidates by deeply analyzing the relevance between the question and each video's content.

This evolution from simple keyword matching to sophisticated embedding-based semantic understanding has dramatically improved the ability of systems to recommend truly relevant videos in response to user questions. Modern systems can understand the intent behind questions, match them to appropriate content regardless of terminology differences, and even identify the most relevant moments within videos that address specific questions.

2 The project

Our university has 53,000 public videos in its media system, a third of which are uploaded to its channel on YouTube. All these videos have automatically created video

transcriptions (some of them with manual corrections) that can be transformed into embeddings and uploaded to a vector database.

We want to create a video recommendation service based on the user's questions that answers with links to the most related videos to a question based on the video transcriptions.

As we have seen, embedding-based approaches have emerged as a powerful alternative to capture the semantics of different texts and, by measuring the similarity between video transcription embeddings and user queries, deliver more accurate and relevant recommendations.

As video transcription texts can be very long, a technique called chunking is used. Chunking is a technique used to divide the transcriptions of videos into smaller segments, so the embeddings to be compared with the questions are shorter segments, enabling more fine-grained analysis and recommendation. Different chunking strategies, such as fixed-length chunking and sentence-based chunking, have been explored in the literature. Chunking is often enhanced by using chunk overlap, a technique that makes consecutive chunks have words in common, which increases the size of the vector database but captures better the content of related words.

The effectiveness of embedding-based systems relies on the choice of embedding model, search strategy, and chunking parameters. Furthermore, most of our video content is in Spanish and most of the questions will be in that language, and most embedding generation models available are tuned to work better in English.

So, selecting the best combination of searching strategy, embedding model and chunking parameters can make a big difference in the results obtained.

2.1 Using Large Language Models to automate the parameter optimization

Large Language Models (LLMs) have demonstrated very good capabilities in natural language processing tasks, including text generation, translation, and question answering. Our theory is that, by leveraging LLMs, it is possible to automate the generation of diverse and relevant queries to compare different configuration parameters, thereby improving the quality of the video recommendation system.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research questions

This study analyzes the feasibility of automating the evaluation of embedding-based video recommendation systems in Spanish by employing LLMs to generate a comprehensive set of queries and systematically testing different model configurations to identify the optimal parameters for delivering accurate video recommendations.

The research questions of this study are:

Q1: How much can the use of an automated system based in LLM generated questions improve the performance of a video recommendation system?

Q2: Which are the best configuration, model and parameters for a video recommendation system for educational videos in Spanish based in user's questions?

Q3: Can we achieve similar results using open source embedding models to the ones obtained with state-of-the-art paid models?

3.2 Procedure

370 videos from the collection were randomly selected, and their transcriptions were uploaded to a database.

These transcriptions were uploaded to ChatGPT-4 with the following prompt: "Generate 10 short-answer questions and their answers based on the text provided below. Return the result in CSV format, with the fields 'question', 'answer', 'video_code'. The questions must include all the necessary context to be understood without having access to the text. The text is:" and the transcription text.

The 3,700 generated questions were stored in the database to be used for the evaluation of different configurations of the retrieval system. The idea is to enter the questions in the retrieval system and see which videos are recommended, comparing the aggregated accuracy of the system in giving back the video from which the question was created.

For a specific configuration of the system and a parameter k (number of retrieved matching embeddings in order), the metrics calculated in the first version of the system were: embed generation time in seconds, retrieval time in seconds to process the 3,700 questions, percentage of cases in which the embedding appearing in the first position matched the correct video, percentage of cases in which the majority of the k embeddings corresponded to the correct video and percentage of cases in which any of the k embeddings corresponded to the correct video.

To have a figure for benchmarking the quality of the retrieval system with embeddings, a Python script was developed to do the same procedure using the BM25 algorithm. BM25 (Best Matching 25) is a ranking function widely used in information retrieval (IR) systems, such as search engines, to rank documents based on their relevance to a given query. It belongs to the family of probabilistic retrieval models and is based on the Bag of Words (BoW) representation. BM25 is an improvement over the older TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) model. This BM25 recommender gave only one answer that corresponded to the correct video for 67.38% of the question bank.

The next step was to select several embedding models to be evaluated. For this we used an open source embedding models leaderboard table available in the Hugging Face website (now available in https://huggingface.co/spaces/mteb/leaderboard_legacy). We selected the Retrieval category and selected several of the multilingual models that performed well with French and Polish languages.

Another Python script using LangChain library was created to calculate the different metrics with several embedding models, different chunking strategies, chunking sizes and overlaps and create with them a local vector database using FAISS. After creating the embeddings of the 3,700 questions and querying the vector database to see which videos were returned for a query, we compared the accuracy of the systems with the different metrics.

After a first evaluation round with fixed parameters (a chunk size of 1000, an overlap of 100 and recursive as the LangChain chunking strategy), we decided to evaluate BAAI/bge-m3 and intfloat/multilingual-e5 (small/base/large) (discarding Jina-embeddings and gte Qwen-2, that gave similar but slightly worse results) and hkunlp/instructor (base/large/xl) as open source models, and the best available embedding model available then from OpenAI, text-embedding-3-large.

Of the different chunking strategies that LangChain offers: fixed chunk size, semantic (in which the text is split at known sentence separating characters) and recursive (in which paragraphs and sentences are split recursively using separating characters -that can be chosen- until the chunk size is met), we decided to incorporate semantic chunking and two recursive strategies with splitting characters in different order.

In the next round we created a metric that added all the inverse distances of the embeddings corresponding to the same video with a weighting depending on their order in the k values, but the improvement in the accuracy was rendered insignificant by the use of rerankers in the next phase.

Later we incorporated a two-stage retrieval model using a reranker model. The system retrieves a higher number of embeddings in the first stage (higher k) and feeds the text associated with them to the reranker model in a second stage, that is slower but more accurate and gives a better result. The k value has to be chosen in a way that the retrieving time is within acceptable values. After trying several reranker models, we chose BAAI/reranker-v2-m3. This led to a significant improvement in the accuracy of the first result and let us add another improvement, mixing the results of the first stage with the results of a traditional BM25 ranker in a small proportion of 10% or less before feeding the documents to the reranker, so, if a question is more keyword based, the results improve.

In a later round we tried to improve the results by changing the library used for chunking to Llama2 and using its chunking strategies, "SimpleNodeParser", "TokenTextSplitter", "SemanticSplitterNodeParser" and "SentenceWindowNodeParser" but

we got no improvement over the best results obtained with LangChain splitters. We also created a chunker with GPT-4 using the OpenAI API, but it was slower and didn't get better results than the best LangChain splitter either.

4 Results

4.1 Initial phase

After selecting the embedding models and the ranges of the parameters to be tested (50, 100 to 800 with 100 spacing, 1000, 1600, 3000, 3200 and 5000), the overlap (0, 10, 20, 40, 50, 80, 90, 99, 100, 160, 180, 200, 250, 275, 300, 320, 350, 370, 375, 390, 450, 490, 500, 550, 590, 640, 650, 690, 700, 750, 790, 975, 1500), the k values (from 2 to 10, 15, 20, 30, 50) and 3 chunking strategies (semantic, recursive 1, recursive 2), we ran 2791 combinations and obtained the following results:

Table 1. Initial accuracy by model.

Model	Accuracy of first result	Accuracy with "Most frequent in k" metric	Average retrieval time all questions
text-embedding-3-large (OpenAI paid)	77.94% (max) 74.24% (avg)	78.1% (max) 71.65% (avg)	2,042 sg
BAAI/bge-m3 (open source)	73.33% (max) 69.21% (avg)	73.7% (max) 64.78% (avg)	90 sg
intfloat/multilingual-e5-large (open source)	Similar to BAAI/bge-m3	Similar to BAAI/bge-m3	90 sg

The average retrieval time for all the questions with text-embedding-3-large is more than an order of magnitude over the time that the other models take.

Table 2. Correct video among first k results

Model	k=3	k=5
text-embedding-3-large (OpenAI paid)	88.38%	92.6%
BAAI/bge-m3 (open source)	86.50%	91.30%
intfloat/multilingual-e5-large (open source)	86.50%	91.30%

The other models get worse results, so they are discarded.

The optimal parameters for text-embedding-3-large are chunk_size=600, overlap=590, chunk strategy=recursive and the retrieval time=2099 seconds. With these parameters the k=3 percentage is 81.9%, not the best result for this metric.

The optimal parameters for BAAI/bge-m3 are chunk_size=400, overlap=390, chunk strategy=recursive and the retrieval time=73.33 seconds. With these parameters the k=3 percentage is 79.34%, not the best result for this metric.

The conclusions from this phase were that we were going to try to optimize the parameters for BAAI/bge-m3 to see if we could achieve or go over the performance of the OpenAI paid model. The improvements obtained by using the aggregated % metric instead of the first result are marginal, so this metric was discarded as the main metric to evaluate the system.

The time the OpenAI model takes is not practical for a production system, but, as the idea was to try to use the open-source models, no effort will be made to optimize it.

The overlap of the best solutions was very high, so the size of the embeddings database was incorporated to the metrics to control if it grew too much and to see if something could be done to make it smaller.

4.2 Reranker

The later trials, made to create a new metric that improved the results of the system by adding the different embedding corresponding to the same video, were discarded when the reranker approach was adopted, as it gave better results, so they are not commented.

A new parameter was introduced, the % of BM25 results fed to the reranker, and a new metric was created, the size of the embeddings database (as stated before).

132 different combinations were tried with the BAAI/bge-m3 model and the BAAI/bge-reranker-v2-m3, trying with $k=10$, 20 and 50 and the best accuracy for the first result was up to 82.81% with 0% of BM25 results, $chunk_size=1300$, $overlap=800$, $chunk_strategy=recursive$ and $k=50$ (with the reranker k becomes a parameter, as it increases the accuracy of the second stage and the retrieval time), but the retrieval time went up also to 882.44 seconds.

Selecting $k=10$, 0% of BM25 results, $chunk_size=1300$ and $overlap=800$, the results are a little worse (81.9%), but the retrieval time goes down to 309.12 seconds and the embedding database size is 20.32 MB instead of 26.96 MB.

So, for the reranker a k value of 10 was selected as a compromise between accuracy and retrieval time.

The conclusion of this phase is that with a reranker the accuracy of the system improves significantly even with an open-source model and that retrieval times can be kept reasonable.

4.3 Optimizing chunking strategy

100 more trials were made trying to optimize the chunking strategy, testing the chunkers of the Llama 2 library and creating a chunker with GPT-4. None of them was better than the recursive or recursive2 strategies of LangChain.

A 5% of the results fed to the reranker came from BM25, as in keyword oriented queries it can improve very much the query result and the performance penalty in other situations is very low. The final results are listed below:

Table 3. Final performance figures.

Accuracy (1st response)	82.23%
Accuracy (top 3 responses)	90.35%
Accuracy (top 5 responses)	93.32%
Retrieval time all questions	297.73 seconds
Database size (317 videos)	20.37 MB

Using SimpleNodeParser from Llama with chunk size=1500, overlap=800 and the same amount of BM25, is a little less accurate (81.84%), is a little bit slower (391.91 seconds) and creates a smaller video database of 15.85 MB.

5 Conclusions and future work

We have created a recommendation system using embeddings and improved its accuracy, from 77% with a paid embeddings model to 81% with a free one.

We have created a system that automates the tuning of the parameters of a system that can be used by any institution of online learning.

The best configuration for the BAAI/bge-m3 model is chunk_size=1500, overlap=800, chunk strategy=recursive, k=10, BM25=5%.

For the future we have to extend the system to support 50,000 videos instead of 400, and several simultaneous users, so we have to move it to a system that can scale. Taking this into account, and after conducting research on what is available on the internet, we installed a Milvus server to store all the encodings.

The problem is that, for large amounts of embeddings, a simple index approach used is not fast enough, so we will have to choose from one of the index alternatives that Milvus provides, as search strategies play a crucial role in efficiently retrieving relevant videos from large-scale databases. Approximate Nearest Neighbor (ANN) search algorithms, such as HNSW and FAISS, are commonly used to accelerate the search process.

However, the performance of these algorithms can be influenced by factors like index size, query volume, and desired accuracy.

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